

CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF CAA (2019) AS A REFUGEE FRAMEWORK IN INDIA

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Abstract: The Citizenship Amendment Act (CAA) of 2019, aimed at providing expedited citizenship to certain religious minorities from Pakistan, Afghanistan, and Bangladesh who entered India before December 2014. This paper critically analyzes the CAA's role within the broader context of refugee law, examining its legislative history, scope, and limitations. Although the Act addresses the historical grievances of specific groups, it has been criticized for its selective criteria, which exclude other vulnerable communities and fail to meet established international standards for refugee protection. This analysis argues that the CAA does not constitute a comprehensive refugee framework but rather a one-time measure for a particular subset of historical refugees. To address India's ongoing refugee challenges, the paper advocates for the development of a more inclusive, holistic, and non-discriminatory refugee law that upholds the principles of international human rights, ensuring equitable protection for all persecuted individuals irrespective of religion or country of origin. This approach would position India as a more responsible and humane actor in regional and global refugee policy.

Key Words - CAA, Refugee, Framework, Constitution, India etc.

I.INTRODUCTION

India is home to refugees from various countries; however, it is not a signatory to the 1951 Refugee Convention and the 1967 Protocol, the backbone of international refugee law. This lack of regulatory structure leaves the treatment of refugees in India based on myriad laws that could not have been intended for this purpose, like the Foreigners Act of 1946 and the Passports Act of 1920. These focus more on the management of foreigners within India's borders and more or less treat refugees merely as illegal immigrants without explicitly considering their particular needs for protection. Although the CAA undoubtedly confers citizenship on a specific group, it renders no long-term relief to other refugee groups who now live in India or may be likely to seek asylum here within the near future. The Act has been so focused that it is more of an ad hoc political step than being an integral part of a long-term refugee protection policy. Khan (2020) express that the exclusionary nature of the CAA also raises certain critical questions regarding whether the Act complies with Indian constitutional principles of equality and non-discrimination, and with international standards.

However, the CAA has sparked significant controversy by arousing questions on its broader implications, especially regarding its exclusion of other communities and the lack of a comprehensive framework for dealing with refugee protection in India. Where the Act is portrayed as a benevolent measure to rescue the persecuted minorities, it is no law on refugees in general but targeted and one-time relief to a particular group of people. The amendment to the citizenship law offers privileged access to citizenship to migrants belonging to particular faiths, thus introducing a distinction on the basis of religion that is seen to violate the right to equality under the Indian Constitution (Jayal, 2022). The exclusion of Muslim refugees like Rohingyas from Myanmar, who are persecuted, has only furthered the debate about the fairness and inclusiveness of the CAA. Critics point out that the religion-based criterion in the Act contravenes India's secular constitution and international refugee protection principles that enunciate a principle of non-discrimination in any form based on religion.

This paper critically analyzes the Citizenship Amendment Act and reviews its strengths and weaknesses concerning the Indian context of refugee protection. It will evaluate whether the CAA can be an entry point leading to a more holistic refugee protection regime or only remains as a one-off remedy for a group. The broader impacts of the CAA in the absence of a comprehensive legal regime on the issue of refugee protection will, therefore, be assessed to propose the need for more inclusive and more sustainable legal measures.

II. CAA AS A REFUGEE PROTECTION MEASURE

The CAA was notified by the Indian Parliament on December 12th, 2019 (Jain, 2022), which led to a significant amendment to the citizenship law of 1955. The CAA came into effect on 10 January 2020 (Project, 2020). The Act grants citizenship of India in respect of the members of specific religious minorities of Hindus, Sikhs, Buddhists, Jains, Parsis, and Christians who have left their countries due to religious persecution in Afghanistan, Bangladesh, and Pakistan and entered India on or before December 31, 2014. The rationale is that these people deserve to be protected and granted citizenship of the country, for they have left their very own countries based on persecution on account of religion owing to being a religious minority in their respective countries.

The Act provides them with legal shield as they are not categorized as "illegal immigrants" under the Foreigners Act of 1946 and the Passport (Entry into India) Act of 1920. Bhattacharjee (2020) states that its primary intention is to provide relief to the ones who flee from religious persecution and have stayed here for years without having status. Though the CAA is pitched as a humanitarian measure, its limited scope thus reveals that it actually functions as a kind of one-time legislative response to a particular refugee crisis instead of being a comprehensive solution to all the refugees in India. Its cutoff date of December 31, 2014, limits its potential beneficiaries to a particular group and excludes anybody from these communities arriving after this date from eligibility for citizenship based upon the CAA. This temporal limitation ensures that the Act focuses on the particular historic situation rather than creating a precedent for future policies on refugees. It does not provide an infrastructure to house future asylum seekers nor to deal with the constant inflow of refugees into India from the same or other neighboring countries. The Act, therefore, cannot be termed a long-term measure toward the overall issue of refugee protection in India.

Apart from this brief time frame, the CAA has applied solely to refugees from three nations: Afghanistan, Bangladesh, and Pakistan. This narrow geographical outlook excludes all other huge refugee populations of India, including populations from Myanmar, Sri Lanka, Tibet, and African countries. For example, the Rohingya Muslim escaping the widespread persecution and violence in Myanmar are not covered by the CAA as it does not take account of Muslim refugees into its citizenship policy. Similarly, the Tamil refugees from Sri Lanka, who have taken refuge in India due to ethnic conflict, are also not included in the CAA. This selective application makes it one time, aimed at redressal of a particular section of refugees but not the overall refugee issue India faces.

Besides, it does not provide any legal procedures for the future asylum seekers irrespective of religious or ethnic backgrounds (Ratha, 2021). It does not have a specific law governing refugees and asylum seekers, nor does the CAA fill this gap. Instead, it offers a solution that's very narrowly defined to apply to only some, leaving out a large number of refugees who continue to reside in India and live without any legal status or protection. The lack of a comprehensive framework leads to the application of general laws to persons that do not fall into any definitions under the CAA; one such example is the Foreigners Act of 1946, wherein they become illegal immigrants and are liable to be deported or detained.

III. CRITICAL ANALYSIS

India has been an easy and traditional destination for the refugee exiles because of the geopolitical situations and historical ethos of sheltering disgruntled populaces. From Tibetans fleeing Chinese oppression to Sri Lankan Tamils escaping civil war, and Rohingya Muslims fleeing violence in Myanmar, India has been a choice for years for different groups seeking refuge. However, India, despite all of this history of providing sanctuary, did not have a comprehensive legal instrument dealing with the needs of refugees and asylum seekers. Also, it is not a signatory to the 1951 United Nations Refugee Convention or its 1967 Protocol, which form the core of international refugee law. India's lack of legal commitment to any of the provisions of these international

mechanisms results in the absence of a legal definition of the term "refugee" in Indian law. The CAA of 2019 brings relief to specific religious communities from Afghanistan, Bangladesh, and Pakistan. Still, it fails to address the gap and highlights the lack of a uniform refugee protection system.

It has been criticized for leaving Muslim refugees out, and it has thus been argued that the exclusion would detract from India's secular ethos. The CAA thus introduces a religious test for Indian citizenship, in contravention of the Constitution, which bars the privileging of religion (Roy, 2020). The present CAA should not be seen as isolated legislation rather it is part of a well-knitted conspiracy aiming to rob secularism, minorities' rights, and social justice through legislative mode (Nagarwal, 2021). India is home to a massive number of refugees from other countries, such as nearly 100,000 Sri Lankan Tamils and tens of thousands of Rohingya Muslims from Myanmar. Still, their status remains unclarified due to the country's lack of such an organized legal structure. Moreover, since the said law has focused on the persecution factor, then the religious minority sects among Muslims, such as Ahmadi, Hazara, etc., are also persecuted in the covered countries. They should have also been included in the purview of the law. Even the Rohingyas and Sri Lankan Tamils are persecuted based on their religious status, why are they not covered, also remains a question. It is also important to note that, majority of the Chakma and Hajong refugees lives in Schedule Tribe areas where the CAA is exempted from implementation, leaving them behind the purview of CAA. The selective choice supports the idea that the CAA is a one-time political measure rather than a proper refugee protection law. The lack of any plans to deal with current or future emergencies for refugees further supports the idea that CAA is not a long-term and holistic refugee solution but rather a short-term measure specially addressed to a particular issue and more importantly gaining electoral gains.

The doctrine known as "nonrefoulement" is partially followed in India at the Centre's discretion. It refers to the rights of refugees to shelter and countries' obligations not to return them to states where they may be persecuted. The legal framework under which refugees exist in India is piecemeal and fragmented. Refugees are governed by the same legislation applicable to foreign nationals, and the laws governing foreigners include the Foreigners Act 1946, the Passport Entry into India Act 1920, which regulate entry, stay, or exit of foreigners. The legislation deals with refugees in the same manner in which it treats illegal immigrants, labelling refugees as violators of immigration laws. Also, the Acts empower the central government to make rules on foreign issues, and the government uses the power of discretion and often exercises it, minding political gains. This puts the refugees in India in a precarious situation of detention and deportation, with added legal insecurity.

Moreover, there is no designated agency to handle the matter of refugees. The UN High Commissioner for Refugees helps and resettles refugees in India, but the role is small in importance as India does not recognize officially the mandate of the UNHCR within its borders. For instance, Tibetan refugees have a stable status due to a special arrangement with the Indian government that enables those refugees to remain in established settlements with identity certificates. However, Sri Lankan Tamils and Rohingyas, among others do not have the same legal security. Tamil refugees in India living in camps on account of fleeing the civil war in Sri Lanka experience severe restrictions on their mobility, employment, and education. Most have been in the camps for over two decades and still do not know how to become citizens or gain permanent residence. The conditions that the Rohingya refugees face are even worse. They are normally seen as illegal immigrants and receive deportations, detentions, and harassments constantly in fear. For example, the Indian authorities have extradited several Rohingya refugees to Myanmar. This action contravenes the principle of non-refoulement, which states that individuals are not returned to a country where they fear persecution. These legal uncertainties expose refugees to exploitation, poverty, and exclusion from services offered in healthcare and education.

Ahmed, (2020), states that the Indian government has termed its refugee policy as flexible and situation-specific, which enables it to adapt to the changing regional circumstances and security threats. For example, the government cites the existence of Rohingya refugees as "nationalists" who "have links to terrorism and illegal activities." Meanwhile, this method is quite different from the international approach that stresses the requirement of a predictable, rights-based framework for the protection of refugees. International law mandates that refugees be protected without regard to religious or racial differences, not to mention nationalities. International law enshrines in each refugee basic rights such as health care, schooling, and employment. Without these rights under India's ad-hoc policies on how to manage the refugees, it has resulted in a service that is haphazard to all these different groups of refugees and denial of proper legal protection for most of them.

The interconnectedness of NRC and CAA is also important to understand. Both the Laws are independent in itself however these two are very much related and complement each other. This narrative on which the CAA is based that differentiates between the deserving 'refugee' (usually Hindu) versus the 'infiltrator' (usually Muslim) comes unstuck when the NRC in Assam ends up producing a longer list of Bengali Hindu refugees whom it terms as 'illegal migrants' (Datta, 2022). Soon after the CAA was adopted, a series of protests against the act began in different parts of India and in some foreign countries (Ranjan, 2023). It was feared that NRC would make the excluded in NRC individuals stateless, however, CAA would protect all, leaving only Muslims behind. This projection of interconnectedness of both the laws are seemingly targeting Muslims. The annulment of citizenship for the 'illegal Bangladeshi migrants', a longstanding geopolitical project like the NRC has been initiated finally and then CAA-2019 negating citizenship eligibility for 'illegal Bangladeshi Muslim migrants' only as a scheme of BJP's political Hindutva (Roy, 2024). Both the laws are criticized as these are used as a tool by the political party in power and gaining electoral benefits out of this.

IV. Conclusion

The CAA is undoubtedly a measure to protect refugees coming from Bangladesh, Afghanistan and Pakistan before 31 December 2014 on account of religious persecution. However, it does not serve as a holistic and general framework for refugee protection. The existing refugee law framework in India is largely a mish-mash, obsolescence, and without consistency. In this context, there is an urgent necessity for an overall refugee law in India that protects all refugees and asylum seekers irrespective of their religion or country of origin. In recent times, however, "secularism" in India has fallen into disrepute (Chandrachud, 2020), which also needs to be upheld through this law.

A comprehensive refugee is the need of the hour, which shall have: 1. Definition of Refugee. The formulation of a legal definition aligned with international norms for "refugee" is very much needed for refugee protection. In this respect, it would offer legal protection to those coming under the ambit of definition. 2. Establish Well-Defined Procedures for Asylum: Any legal framework would also provide asylum-seeking procedures- right to a fair hearing, and the right to appeal any adverse decision. This will ensure a structured and transparent channel for protection in India. 3. Non-Refoulement: Any refugee law must include the principle of non-refoulement, whereby refugees may not be forcibly sent back to countries where they will be persecuted or subjected to serious harm. 4. Basic Rights and Access to Services: Refugees should access basic health services, education, and employment rights. A wide-ranging law should include provisions to allow refugees to lead dignified lives while in India, irrespective of their long-term status. 5. Citizenship or Permanent Residency: For those refugees staying for very long intervals, like Tibetan and Sri Lanka refugees, there should be a legal channel towards citizenship or permanent residency in India. In that way, they will be at par with the Indian citizenry and will be able to make substantial contributions to the Indian economy and culture. 6. Include Provisions to Avoid Discrimination: A proper refugee law should ensure all refugees receive equal treatment without any discrimination on religion, race, or ethnicity to avoid arbitrary application of protection like in the case of CAA, which was applied selectively and arbitrarily.

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